

Density, viscosity and conductance measurement of pyrazinamide in aqueous solution in presence and absence of additives at 308.15 K

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Abstract : The density, viscosity and conductance of drug pyrazinamide in aqueous solution at 308.15 K have been determined and analyzed in presence as well as in absence of additive viz. KCl, NaCl and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The density results are used to evaluate the apparent and partial molar volumes. Viscosity results are used to calculate Jones-Dole viscosity, β -coefficient. The study is of immense use for pharmacological applications of drug.

Keywords : Pyrazinamide, viscosity, β -coefficient, partial molar volume, molar conductance.

Introduction

Medicinally important drugs interact with various ions, molecules present in the biological system. The mechanism of interaction is complex and involves several factors. Most of the pharmacological reactions are taking place in aqueous media¹. The types of interactions between solute-solvent, solvent-solvent etc. can be well understood from the density, viscometric determination. Pyrazinamide is an antibiotic; it is used for the treatment tuberculosis (TB). Recently^{2,3} there are various research articles published which are related with density, viscometric and conductometric measurement of medicinal drugs in various media.

Structure of PZA

Experimental

The medicinal drug pyrazinamide was used as such and KCl, NaCl and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ after drying in oven. The chemicals were of S.D. fine chemicals Ltd. Doubly distilled water was used for the preparation of solutions. The density of different solution mixtures were measured with a set of three pycnometers with single arm capillary and single pan electronic balance (Contech, CA, Mumbai)

with a precision of 0.0001 g. The weighing was repeated thrice to ensure the accuracy in weights with a little of time. The reproducibility of the result was close to 100%. Viscosity measurements were performed by using Ostwald's viscometer. The viscometer was clamped vertically in a thermostat controlled water bath at 308.15 K. The measurement of flow time of the solution between the two points on the viscometer was performed at least five times for each solution and the results were averaged. The conductance of all solutions was measured by using conductometer of Elico make (model CM 180) the conductance measurement for added drug and additive were repeated at least four times.

Results and discussion

The properties of PZA in aqueous solution without any additives are shown in Table 1. This shows that the densities increase with increase in concentration. The variation on viscosity is not linear, but conductance increases with concentration of PZA. The conductivity of drug is due to HCl, the drug dissociated to give protonated pyrazinamide and chloride ions. The densities of PZA in presence of additives show a definite trend (Table 2). There is increase in density with increase in concentration of PZA and as well as of additives. The variation observed is $\text{NaCl} < \text{KCl} < \text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which is obvious similar increase in densities with increase in concentration of salt for ternary mixture of glycol + H_2O + LiCl or LiBr was reported by Tsai⁴.

Table 1. Properties of pyrazinamide in absence of additives

Concentration (M) →	0.002 (M) PZA	0.004 (M) PZA	0.006 (M) PZA	0.008 (M) PZA
Properties ↓				
Density (g/ml)	0.99415	0.99477	0.99569	0.99586
Viscosity (CP)	0.70212	0.71080	0.70398	0.72750
Conductance (mS)	0.0390	0.0450	0.0490	0.074

Table 2. Densities of pyrazinamide in presence of additives

PZA (M)	KCl (M)				NaCl (M)				Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O (M)			
	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08
0.002	0.99543	0.99645	0.99792	0.99814	0.99479	0.99620	0.99721	0.99769	0.99785	0.99969	1.00288	1.00688
0.004	0.99607	0.99661	0.99790	0.99821	0.99497	0.99634	0.99731	0.99771	0.99824	0.99972	1.00315	1.00722
0.006	0.99633	0.99664	0.99797	0.99859	0.99587	0.99640	0.99754	0.99781	0.99882	1.00044	1.00354	1.00731
0.010	0.99642	0.99745	0.99801	0.99867	0.99619	0.99651	0.99760	0.99794	0.99971	1.00127	1.00375	1.00744

The density data was used to calculate apparent molar volume V_ϕ using eq. (1).

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho\rho_0} + \frac{M_2}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where M_2 , C , ρ and ρ_0 are the molar mass of drug, concentration (mol kg⁻¹) and densities of the solution and the solvent respectively. The apparent molar volumes are used to calculate limiting apparent volume V_ϕ^0 using following equation and least square method.

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v C \quad (2)$$

The values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v are given in Table 3. V_ϕ^0 values of PZA-HCl in presence and absence of additives are found to be negative. Its value increase in magnitude with

increase in concentration of additives. S_v is a measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interactions. The S_v is found to be negative for the PZA-HCl in absence of additives. The S_v values in presence of additive becomes positive and increases with increase in concentration of additives but we observed that at 0.08 M of NaCl and Cu(NO₃)₂.3H₂O the values is found to be negative again. This may be due to aggregation of molecules which results in decrease the number of ions. It is well established that S_v depend of solute, solvent and temperatures.

The trend in viscosity shows that it increases with increase in concentration of additives salt in the order NaCl < KCl < Cu(NO₃)₂.3H₂O. The viscosity values in presence of fixed concentration of additives first decrease and then increases (see Table 4). The viscosity data was used to calculate Jones-Dole parameter⁶.

$$\eta_r - 1 = A\sqrt{c} + B \quad (3)$$

where η_r is relative viscosity, A and B are Falkenhagen and Jones-Dole coefficients⁷.

B -Viscosity coefficient is measure of the effective hydrodynamic volume of the solvated ions. It denotes the order or disorder by the ions into solvent structure. In the present study, we observe that B -coefficient is negative for only PZA-HCl without any additive, but it is becomes positive for all additives at all concentration range and varies between 0.02407 to 1.925808 except 0.08 M NaCl, the value found to be negative (see Table 5). A coefficient values for PZA-HCl, without additives are positive and in presence of additive are negative with few exceptions.

Table 3. Limiting partial molar volume in presence and absence of additives

Additives	Concentration (M)	S_v	V_ϕ^0
Without additives	-	-470.82	-87.93
KCl	0.02	10883.78	-1082.16
	0.04	19791.11	-1982.93
	0.06	28862.73	-2910.74
	0.08	31188.55	-3276.26
NaCl	0.02	6664.59	-663.338
	0.04	18938.95	-1982.93
	0.06	30200.76	-3063.78
	0.08	-24443.8	-2567.48
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O	0.02	31047.94	-3102.43
	0.04	38572.28	-4224.64
	0.06	70220.87	-7363.37
	0.08	-100223.7	-10576.5

Table 4. Viscosities of pyrazinamide in presence of additives

PZA (M)	KCl (M)				NaCl (M)				Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O (M)			
	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08
0.002	0.7276	0.72937	0.72958	0.72230	0.71992	0.72102	0.72226	0.69803	0.76337	0.73187	0.74321	0.74617
0.004	0.72022	0.71150	0.72150	0.72232	0.72028	0.69702	0.69821	0.70556	0.73903	0.73187	0.75039	0.74568
0.006	0.75416	0.72167	0.72186	0.73097	0.72020	0.69658	0.69772	0.76472	0.73799	0.74066	0.74266	0.75420
0.010	0.72120	0.73816	0.72209	0.72297	0.72036	0.69649	0.69797	0.69785	0.73812	0.73302	0.75165	0.75389

Table 5. Viscosity B-coefficient in presence and absence of additives

	Concentration (M)	A	B
Without additives	-	10.64318	-0.98206
KCl	0.02	-1.47712	0.335821
	0.04	0.535217	0.071236
	0.06	-4.56962	0.437101
	0.08	-0.14238	0.11304
NaCl	0.02	-0.10744	0.02407
	0.04	-5.50086	0.100508
	0.06	-5.81447	0.148855
	0.08	10.13636	-0.83695
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O	0.02	-18.6054	1.925808
	0.04	-2.93525	0.51753
	0.06	-6.03299	1.002149
	0.08		

towards electrode. Again we calculate λ_0 using least square method for PZA-HCl in presence of additive and represented in Table 7. These λ_0 are ascertained to following equations.

The physical and chemical properties depend on extent of solvation. There are various factors such as polarity, capacity to form hydrogen bond, functional groups present, ionic size, which decides the conductance behavior of a compound in water. In presence of electrolyte, the medicinal drug may interact with it electrostatically or may form a complex ion.

Table 6. Conductance (mhos/cm) of pyrazinamide in presence of additives

PZA (M)	KCl (M)				NaCl (M)				Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O (M)			
	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08
0.002	3.30	6.15	9.67	12.15	2.014	5.31	7.91	9.84	4.63	8.55	11.95	15.88
0.004	3.31	6.50	9.23	12.07	2.90	5.28	7.64	9.78	4.64	8.69	12.08	15.58
0.006	3.45	6.61	9.60	12.08	3.08	5.34	7.61	9.81	4.59	8.52	11.79	15.47
0.010	3.44	6.42	9.51	12.22	2.87	5.24	7.73	9.90	4.61	8.62	12.10	15.51

The conductance of PZA-HCl in absence and presence of additives were measured and represented in Table 6. PZA-HCl is a hydrochloride salt, it show conductance due to ion formation. Limiting molar conductance λ_0 was evaluated using Onsager relations. The λ_0 value obtained by plotting (not shown) λ against \sqrt{c} in absences of additives was 26.66 mhos. Where c is the concentration of PZA-HCl. These values indicate that with increase in concentration of NaCl and KCl conductance increases, but keeping concentration of NaCl and KCl constant, and varying the concentration of PZA-HCl, we observed that a little increase in conductance and at 0.01 M PZA-HCl, it decreases. This may be due to the formation of ion association which retards the measurement ion

Table 7. Limiting conductance of pyrazinamide in presence and absence of additives

PZA	Concentration (M)	λ_0	$\lambda - \lambda_0$
Without additives	-	26.66025	-
KCl	0.02	2464.295	2431.6348
	0.04	4110.240	4584.3638
	0.06	7208.855	7182.1948
	0.08	9101.616	9014.9558
NaCl	0.02	1556.705	1530.0448
	0.04	3988.357	3961.6975
	0.06	5915.851	5889.19075
	0.08	7371.504	7344.84375
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O	0.02	3479.123	3452.46275
	0.04	6432.261	6405.60075
	0.06	8975.294	8948.63375
	0.08	11913.282	11886.62175

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